

STRESS MANAGEMENT AMONG ADOLESCENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR LOCUS OF CONTROL

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Paper Received On: 20 NOVEMBER 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 DECEMBER 2025

Published On: 01 JANUARY 2026

Abstract

This descriptive study investigates the relationship between stress management and locus of control among adolescents. The sample comprised 80 students (40 males and 40 females) drawn randomly from schools in the Amritsar district of Punjab state. The study employed the Stress Management Scale (SMS) by Pushpraj Singh and Anjali Srivastava (1997) and the Hindi version of Rotter's Locus of Control Scale (1996). Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation and t-test were used to analyze the data. Results indicated no significant correlation between stress management and locus of control. Gender differences were found in stress management, with males scoring higher than females, while locale did not significantly influence either variable. Significant differences in stress management were observed in relation to locus of control, with students having an external locus of control showing higher stress management scores. The study highlights implications for teachers in guiding adolescents to cope effectively with stress and develop adaptive coping strategies.

Keywords: *Stress Management, Locus of Control, Coping Strategies, Adolescents, Gender, Locale*

Introduction

The academic and social landscape confronting today's adolescents has grown significantly more challenging. Rapid technological advancements, increased academic competition, heightened parental expectations, peer pressure, and pervasive social media exposure are contributing to unprecedented levels of stress among young people (Prajapati & Bharadwaj, 2021). Adolescence, a stage marked by rapid biological, emotional, and cognitive development, is particularly sensitive to these pressures. Young people often experience heightened psychological vulnerability as they attempt to navigate issues of identity,

independence, academic achievement and social relationships. Among adolescents, chronic stress is associated with anxiety, academic difficulties, withdrawal, irritability, depression and impaired decision-making.

Given these challenges, psychological constructs such as stress, stress management and locus of control play an essential role in determining how adolescents interpret stressors and manage adverse situations. These three constructs are the crucial factors influencing adolescents' academic performance, emotional stability and coping capabilities. Understanding these constructs and their interrelationships is essential for promoting adolescent well-being and ensuring positive developmental outcomes.

Conceptualizing Stress in Adolescence

Stress has been analyzed extensively across disciplines such as psychology, physiology, medicine, and behavioral sciences. Selye (1956) defined stress as the body's nonspecific response to any demand placed upon it, emphasizing its physiological basis. Lazarus (1966) later reconceptualized stress as a cognitive and emotional process through which individuals evaluate whether environmental demands exceed their personal resources. According to this transactional model, stress is not inherent in events themselves but arises from individuals' perceptions and interpretations.

Stress can be positive, motivating individuals toward growth, or negative, demotivating and distress feeling, but persistent or excessive stress disrupts emotional balance and impairs functioning. Adolescents, due to developmental transitions, often experience heightened distress manifested through emotional, cognitive, and behavioral symptoms such as anxiety, irritability, withdrawal, and reduced concentration (Spielberger, 1979; Wolf & Godell, 1968). Adolescents face various academic, social, familial, and personal challenges that may trigger stress. Major adolescent stressors include:

- academic pressure and competitive examinations
- peer relationships, social comparison, and bullying
- parental expectations, family conflict, and communication gaps
- body image concerns and identity formation
- social media influence and digital stress
- risk behaviors

When these stressors remain unaddressed, they may impede academic achievement, disrupt emotional well-being and influence long-term psychosocial development. Stress management, therefore, becomes a crucial component of adolescent well-being.

Stress Management and Coping Strategies

Stress management refers to the cognitive, behavioral, and emotional strategies individuals use to reduce psychological distress and enhance their ability to cope with challenges. Scholars describe stress management as a broad set of cognitive, emotional and behavioral strategies used to regulate stress responses and enhance adaptive functioning (Cofer & Appley, 1964; McGrath, 1970). Adolescents employ a range of coping behaviors such as problem-solving, emotional regulation, cognitive restructuring and help-seeking into stress. Effective stress management contributes to emotional stability, mental resilience, and improved academic functioning. Adolescents who utilize adaptive coping strategies tend to demonstrate higher self-efficacy, emotional resilience, and better interpersonal adjustment.

Modern research consistently shows that adolescents and young adults use a variety of stress-management and coping strategies to handle academic and life pressures. For instance, increasing emphasis has been placed on mindfulness, physical activity, social support, and structured coping techniques. Three principal types of coping strategies are:

- **Problem-focused coping:** Strategies aimed at addressing the source of stress, such as planning, problem-solving, and time management.
- **Emotion-focused coping:** Strategies designed to manage emotional responses, including relaxation techniques, cognitive reframing, and seeking social support.
- **Avoidance coping:** Behaviors such as denial, withdrawal, or procrastination that may offer temporary relief but often exacerbate stress in the long term.

Effective coping promotes personal growth, emotional maturity and psychological stability, whereas ineffective coping increases vulnerability to mental-health difficulties (Lazarus, 1966). Parents, teachers and counselors significantly shape adolescents' coping abilities. Supportive homes, constructive communication, guidance in problem-solving, and positive school environments serve as protective factors (Prajapati & Bharadwaj, 2021). Institutions increasingly incorporate life skills, mindfulness, yoga, and counseling into their curricula to strengthen students' emotional and mental well-being (Sharma & Singh, 2020). These practices decrease stress related symptoms, promote physiological relaxation and improve emotional stability by activating the parasympathetic nervous system.

Locus of Control and Adolescent Development

Locus of control refers to individuals' generalized beliefs about the extent to which they can control outcomes in their lives. Originally conceptualized by Rotter (1966), it refers to the extent to which individuals believe that life outcomes are contingent on their own efforts, abilities and actions (internal control) or on external forces such as fate, luck, chance, or powerful external agents. Research suggests that adolescents with an internal locus of control demonstrate higher resilience, stronger coping mechanisms, lower anxiety, and greater problem-solving efficiency (Lefcourt, 1976; Powell & Vega, 1973). Conversely, those with an external orientation often exhibit helplessness, dependency, avoidance, and difficulty adapting to stressful events (Phares, 1979; Zimbardo, 1985).

This psychological orientation significantly influences motivation, responsibility, and emotional adjustment. Adolescents with an internal locus of control often display higher self-confidence, perseverance, and proactive behavior (Lefcourt, 1976). Those with an external locus of control may experience helplessness, dependency, avoidance, and heightened stress. Research consistently demonstrates that locus of control plays a crucial role in how individuals perceive stress and manage challenges. Internally oriented individuals approach stressors as manageable, exert effort to resolve problems, rely more on problem-focused coping, exhibit lower levels of anxiety and emotional distress (Powell & Vega, 1973; Phares, 1979). Contrary to this, externally oriented individuals perceive stressors as uncontrollable, show passivity or avoidance, experience greater emotional turmoil and demonstrate lower academic motivation (Zimbardo, 1985).

Thus, locus of control is closely linked to adolescents' stress responses, coping styles and overall psychological adaptation.

Review of Related Literature

The review of related studies is divided and presented under the following major heads:

- Studies Related to Stress Management
- Studies Related to Locus of Control
- Studies Related to Stress Management and Locus of Control

Studies Related to Stress Management

Aminabhavi and Triveni (2000) conducted a study on bank employees and found that age, sex, and coping strategies did not significantly influence occupational stress.

Husnain, Sliahnawaz and Shukla (2001) assessed coping strategies across engineers, managers and teachers reporting no significant differences among these groups. Results revealed that the most preferred strategies were extra-resistive and inter-persistent coping. Further, results revealed that male teachers coped more effectively with everyday demands and stressors compared to female teachers.

Aujla, Harshpinder, Sandhu and Gill (2004) studied stress management techniques used by working and non-working women in Ludhiana and found that planning and relaxation were the most preferred strategies.

Kochhar and Khetarpal (2006) reported a negative relationship between job satisfaction and occupational stress among college teachers. They found that permanent teachers demonstrated better coping abilities than temporary teachers.

Eniola and Busari (2007) found significant difference in stress levels between totally blind and partially sighted students following stress management training.

Alzahem, Molen and De Boer (2014) reviewed stress management programs for dental students and noted that interventions typically targeted fear of failure, workload pressure and coping techniques.

Dixit and Garg (2017) found that urban students experienced higher academic stress than rural students and that boys reported higher academic stress than girls.

Kassymova, Kosherbayeva, Sangilbayev and Schachl (2018) emphasized the benefits of stress management courses and extracurricular activities for students and teachers.

Zaichkousky and Fuchs (2021) demonstrated the effectiveness of biofeedback-assisted self-regulation in managing physical stress and improving athletic performance.

Mustafa, Umar, Mustafa and Atta (2024) conducted a study on relationship between perceived stress, locus of control and psychological well-being among medical students and found a strong negative correlation between perceived stress and psychological well-being. Additionally, a significant negative relationship was found between perceived stress and internal locus of control.

Studies Related to Locus of Control

Brown, Mulhern and Joseph (2002) found that firefighters with an external locus of control experienced higher psychological distress, particularly when exposed to stressful incidents.

Chou-Kang, Chi-Sheng, Chiek-Peng and Ching-Yun (2005) reported that locus of control moderated the relationship between job stress, job satisfaction and turnover intentions among hospital employees.

Panuelis and Claxton (2008) found positive correlations among happiness, creative ideation and internal locus of control.

Breet, Myburgh and Poggenpoel (2010) demonstrated that adolescent boys with an external locus of control exhibited significantly higher aggression.

Bulus and Mustafa (2011) found that locus of control predicted goal orientations and academic achievement among prospective teachers.

Zaidi and Moksini (2013) reported gender differences in locus of control among Pakistani undergraduate students, with men scoring higher on internal locus of control.

Arslan and Akin (2014) found that metacognition predicted academic locus of control, especially among students with an internal orientation.

Moreland, Felton, Hanson, Jackson and Dumas (2016) reported that increased parental internal locus of control improved child behavior over an eight-week program.

Qadri, Hassan and Sheikh (2017) demonstrated the mediating role of internal locus of control and job stress between spiritual intelligence and job performance.

Opiyo (2018) found that internal locus of control significantly influenced employees' perceptions of stress management effectiveness.

Sinha, Bhattacharya and Sharma (2019) found that individuals with an internal locus of control experienced lower job stress and higher job satisfaction.

Srivastava and Kapoor (2021) noted that locus of control significantly moderated the relationship between organizational role stress and psychological well-being.

Auliya, Zaharuddin and Darmayanti (2023) examined the influence of internal locus of control and academic self-efficacy on academic adjustment among students at the faculty of Psychology UIN Raden Fatah Palembang. Results showed that internal locus of control and academic self-efficacy significantly contributed to academic adjustment, suggesting that students with stronger internal control beliefs adapt better to academic demands and environmental pressures.

Jain and Lokesh (2023) conducted a study among Indian young adults and examined perceived parenting styles, locus of control and coping strategies. It found that parenting styles were related to individuals' locus of control and their choice of coping mechanisms-

underscoring that locus of control development may be influenced by early environment and that control orientation affects coping behavior later.

Yiming, Shi, Alghadi, Kayani and Biasutti (2023) conducted a study on social support and self-efficacy as mediators between internal locus of control and adolescents' physical activity. The results displayed that physical activity is positively affected by locus of control, self-efficacy, and social support. Both self-efficacy and social support are positively associated with locus of control and physical activity.

Thus, research supports the theoretical position that locus of control remains a key psychological variable in understanding adjustment, coping, and well-being among adolescents and young adults in diverse contexts.

Studies Related to Stress Management and Locus of Control

Haine, Ayers, Sandler, Wolchik and Weyer (2003) observed that self-esteem, rather than locus of control, mediated the relationship between stress and internalizing problems among bereaved children.

Kauts and Mittu (2011) found that teacher effectiveness varied across different stress and locus of control levels, with highly stressed teachers showing better effectiveness.

Ahman, Mohammad and Raheela (2012) reported that teachers with an internal locus of control experienced lower levels of stress.

Habeeb (2016) reported moderate stress levels and predominantly internal locus of control among higher secondary students.

Ogolla, Aloka and Raburu (2016) found that principals with an internal locus of control had significantly higher stress management scores.

Rose and Vega (2017) demonstrated that stress management interventions could alter locus of control orientation and anxiety levels.

Karaman, Lerma, Vela and Watson (2019) found that locus of control, life satisfaction and gender as predictors of academic stress.

Qi, Lizelle and Villanueva (2024) conducted a study entitled "Locus of control and stress coping mechanisms: towards developing a psychological resilience program for athletes". Results showed that athletes attribute outcomes to factors like internal control, belief in powerful others, and chance. Self-assessment of their locus of control did not significantly vary based on factors like sex, age, sports division, or years of playing experience.

Despite substantial theoretical literature on stress, coping strategies and locus of control, empirical studies examining the relationship between stress management and locus of control among adolescents remain limited. Understanding this relationship is important because locus of control is consistently identified as a strong predictor of stress management skills and emotional resilience. Adolescents with an internal locus of control are more likely to take responsibility for their actions, engage in effective coping, and maintain confidence in challenging situations.

Therefore, exploring this relationship can provide valuable insights for educators, parents, counselors, and policymakers aiming to promote adolescent mental health. The findings will contribute to a better understanding of how psychological orientations influence coping abilities and will offer practical implications for designing and developing school-based interventions that foster healthy internal control, emotional stability, and adaptive functioning in young learners.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the relationship between stress management and locus of control among adolescents.
2. To examine stress management among adolescents with respect to gender.
3. To examine stress management among adolescents with respect to locale.
4. To study locus of control among adolescents with respect to gender.
5. To study locus of control among adolescents with respect to locale.
6. To examine stress management among adolescents in relation to their locus of control.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There exists significant relationship between stress management and locus of control of adolescents
2. There exists significant difference in the mean scores of stress management among adolescents with respect to gender.
3. There exists significant difference in the mean scores of stress management among adolescents with respect to locale.
4. There exists significant difference in the mean scores of locus of control among adolescents with respect to gender.

5. There exists significant difference in the mean scores of locus of control among adolescents with respect to locale.
6. There exists significant difference in the mean scores of stress management among adolescents in relation to their locus of control.

Research Design

In the present study descriptive survey method was used.

Sample

A sample of 80 adolescents has been drawn randomly from different schools of Amritsar district. Equal numbers of boys and girls were included in the sample. Random sampling ensured representation across urban and rural areas.

Tools Used

1. Stress Management Scale (SMS) by Singh and Srivastava (1997)
2. Rotter's Locus of Control (1996)

Statistical Techniques Used

- Descriptive statistical techniques such as mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis
- Co-efficient of correlation
- t-test

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Hypothesis 1 : There exists a significant relationship between stress management and locus of control of adolescents.

This hypothesis was framed to find out the relationship between stress management and locus of control of adolescents. The hypothesis has been tested by applying Pearson Correlation to see the relationship between stress management and locus of control. The outcomes of the analysis have been reported in table 1.

Table 1: Pearson Correlation between Stress Management and Locus of Control

Variable	N	Coefficient of Correlation (r)	Inference
Stress Management	80	0.215	insignificant
Locus of Control	80		

The correlation coefficient ($r = 0.215$) is positive but not significant. This indicates that there exists a positive and insignificant relationship between stress management and locus of

control. Hence, the hypothesis "There exists significant relationship between stress management and locus of control of adolescents" stands rejected.

Interpretation: Insignificant relationship; hypothesis rejected.

This result aligns with the result of studies conducted by Ahman, Mohammad and Raheela (2012) and Ogolla, Aloka and Raburu (2016),), indicating variability in stress coping strategies regardless of locus of control.

Hypothesis 2: There exists a significant difference in the mean scores of stress management among adolescents with respect to gender.

This hypothesis was framed to find out the difference between stress management of adolescent male and female students. The hypothesis has been tested by applying 't-test' to the mean scores and the outcomes of the analysis have been reported in table 2.

Table 2 : Mean Scores of Stress Management of Male and Female Adolescents

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	SE _M	t-value
Stress Management	Male	40	107.8	9.8767	1.5616	4.094 (p < .01)
	Female	40	99.625	7.8697	1.2443	

Males scored significantly higher in stress management than females; mean scores of both male and female students are 107.8 and 99.625 respectively. The calculated value of 't' is 4.094 which is significant at 0.01 level of significance. This means that the mean difference is significant. Hence, hypothesis 2 "There exists a significant difference in the mean scores of stress management among adolescents with respect to gender" is accepted.

Interpretation: Significant difference; hypothesis accepted.

The result is supported by Aujla, Harshpinder, Sandhu and Gill (2004), suggesting males cope more actively with ordinary stressors while females rely on emotional and social support for stress relief. The probable reason may be males are more capable of coping with ordinary demands and stressors of life as compared to females. Whether its friends, family or a support group, women like to tell their stories but men often seek an escape activity to get relief from stress and create a relaxing diversion to get away.

Hypothesis 3 : There exists a significant difference in the mean scores of stress management among adolescents with respect to locale.

This hypothesis was framed to find out difference in the mean scores of stress management of adolescent students of urban and rural area. This hypothesis has been tested by applying 't'

test' to the mean scores of adolescent students with respect to locale. The outcomes of the analysis have been reported in table 3

Table 3: Mean Scores of Stress Management Among Adolescents with Respect to Locale

Variable	Locale	N	Mean	SD	SE _M	t-value
Stress Management	Urban	40	103.425	10.5122	1.6621	0.261
	Rural	40	104	9.1147	1.4412	

Table 3 depicts the difference in the mean scores of stress management of adolescent students with respect to locale. It is found that the mean scores of both urban and rural students are 103.425 and 104 respectively. The calculated value of t is 0.261 which is insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence. Hence, hypothesis 3 "There exists a significant difference in the mean scores of stress management among adolescents with respect to locale" stands rejected.

Interpretation: No significant difference; hypothesis rejected.

This result is consistent with the findings of Dixit and Garg (2017), reflecting equal educational exposure and opportunities both in rural and urban areas. The reason may be that in earlier times the education system was not good in the rural areas and the parents of students were not well educated but now the education system has improved in both areas and people are well aware and educated. Thus the better education system and similar cultural exposure may explain this similarity.

Hypothesis 4: There exists a significant difference in the mean scores of locus of control among adolescents with respect to gender.

This hypothesis was framed to find out difference in the mean scores of locus of control of male and female adolescents. The hypothesis has been tested by applying t-test to the mean scores of adolescent students with respect to gender and outcomes of the analysis have been reported in table 4.

Table 4 : Mean Scores of Locus of Control among Adolescents with Respect to Gender

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	SE _M	t-value
Locus of Control	Male	40	12.25	1.5648	0.2474	0.93
	Female	40	11.975	1.025	0.1621	

Table 4 depicts the difference in the mean scores of locus of control of adolescent students with respect to gender. It is found that mean scores of male is 12.25 and female is 11.975. The calculated value of 't' is 0.93 which is insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence. This means that the mean difference is not significant. Hence, hypothesis 4 "There exists significant difference in the mean scores of locus of control among adolescents with respect to gender" is not accepted.

Interpretation: No significant difference; hypothesis rejected.

Studies conducted by Zaidi and Moxsin (2013) and Manichander (2019) confirmed this result. The reason may be that education helps the adolescents to identify their potential and fulfill their responsibility more efficiently and they learn to control and believe in themselves. So educational level and self-awareness may influence adolescents' locus of control more than gender.

Hypothesis 5: There exists a significant difference in the mean scores of locus of control among adolescents with respect to locale.

This hypothesis was framed to find out difference in the mean scores of locus of control of adolescent students of urban and rural area. The hypothesis has been tested by applying 't-test' to the mean scores of adolescents. The outcomes of the analysis have been reported in table 5.

Table 5 : Mean Scores of Locus of Control among Adolescents with Respect to Locale

Variable	Locale	N	Mean	SD	SE _M	t-value
Locus of Control	Urban	40	12.325	1.5589	0.2465	1.448
	Rural	40	11.9	1.0077	0.1593	

Table 5 depicts the difference in the mean scores of locus of control of adolescent students with respect to locale. It is found that mean scores of both urban and rural area students are 12.325 and 11.9. The calculated value of t is 1.448 which is insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence. This means that the mean difference is not significant. Hence, hypothesis 5 "There exists significant difference in the mean scores of locus of control among adolescents with respect to locale" is not accepted.

Interpretation: No significant difference; hypothesis rejected.

Result is supported by Naik (2015) and Manichander (2019). The reason may be found out that due to globalization, rural and urban area gaps have been diminished and now rural

areas too have a good education system, healthcare and income facilities. So similarity in culture, education and socioeconomic factors may account for this result.

Hypothesis 6 : There exists a significant difference in the mean scores of stress management among adolescents in relation to locus of control.

This hypothesis was framed to find out difference in the mean scores of stress management of adolescents in relation to their locus of control. The hypothesis has been tested by applying 't-test' to the mean scores and the outcomes of the analysis have been reported in table 6

Table 6 : Mean Scores of Stress Management of Adolescents in Relation to Their Locus of Control

Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD	SE _M	t-value
Locus of Control	Internal	56	102.089	9.106	1.2168	2.33
	External	24	107.5	10.4341	2.1298	

Table 6 depicts the difference in the mean scores of stress management of adolescent students in relation to locus of control. It is found that the mean scores of stress management of students having internal locus of control is 102.089 and having external locus of control is 107.5. The calculated 't' value is 2.33 which is significant at 0.05 level of confidence. Therefore, hypothesis 6 "There exists significant difference in the mean scores of stress management of adolescents in relation to their locus of control" is accepted.

Interpretation: Students with external locus of control scored higher in stress management than those with internal locus.; Significant difference; hypothesis accepted.

Kauts and Mittu (2011) and Habeeb (2016) supported this result suggesting coping strategies vary with perceived control. The probable reason may be adolescents with external locus of control believe in external forces for their success. They feel that they are victims of circumstances. They often look outside themselves or believe their limited intellect is the reason for their failure and the adolescents with internal locus of control are more likely to manage their stresses for they believe that whatever the outcome of the event is as a result of their own resources & ability.

Findings and Conclusions

1. Relationship between Stress Management and Locus of Control

- The coefficient of correlation (r) between stress management and locus of control was found to be 0.215, which is insignificant.

- Conclusion: No significant relationship exists between stress management and locus of control among adolescents.

2. Stress Management by Gender

- Mean scores: Male = 107.8, Female = 99.625
- Standard deviation: Male = 9.8767, Female = 7.8697
- Conclusion: Gender plays a role in stress management among adolescents. There is a significant difference in stress management between male and female adolescents. Males demonstrated significantly higher stress management than females.

3. Stress Management by Locale

- Mean scores: Urban = 103.425, Rural = 104
- Standard deviation: Urban = 10.5122, Rural = 9.1147
- Conclusion: No significant difference exists in stress management between urban and rural adolescents.

4. Locus of Control by Gender

- Mean scores: Male = 12.25, Female = 11.975
- Standard deviation: Male = 1.5648, Female = 1.025
- Conclusion: No significant difference exists in locus of control of male and female adolescents. Locale has no significant effect on stress management

5. Locus of Control by Locale

- Mean scores: Urban = 12.325, Rural = 11.9
- Standard deviation: Urban = 1.5589, Rural = 1.0077
- Conclusion: No significant difference exists in locus of control between urban and rural adolescents. Locale has no significant effect on locus of control.

6. Stress Management in Relation to Locus of Control

- Mean scores: Internal = 102.089, External = 107.5
- Standard deviation: Internal = 9.106, External = 10.4341
- Conclusion: There is significant difference in stress management among adolescents in relation to their locus of control. Locus of control is related to stress management, with external locus students reporting higher stress management scores than students with internal locus of control.

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